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ASSESSING NOISE POLLUTION IN CTU MOALBOAL NEW ADMINISTRATION BUILDING 4TH FLOOR CLASSROOMS

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ABSTRACT

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Noise pollution in educational spaces significantly impacts students' academic performance and overall well-being. This study investigates noise levels in classrooms at Cebu Technological University - Moalboal, focusing on factors such as room placement and equipment. Measurements reveal that sound levels exceed the World Health Organization's recommended maximum of 35 dB, with Room 05 being the noisiest due to external traffic. Furthermore, strong correlations between outdoor noise and indoor levels suggest that external factors heavily influence classroom acoustics. The findings emphasize the necessity for effective interventions to mitigate noise pollution, thereby enhancing the educational experience. Proposed recommendations include Implementation of sound insulation enhancements, elevate awareness and training on noise management, and as well as the collaboration with acoustic experts. Strategic classroom design and sound management are essential to foster conducive learning environments. Collectively, these measures can significantly improve students' focus and academic success, addressing a critical yet often overlooked issue in education.

Keywords: *Noise Pollution, Learning Environment, Academic Performance, Classroom Acoustics, Sound Measurement, Interventions, Sound Insulation*

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Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SCOPE

INTRODUCTION

Rationale

Noise pollution in educational spaces is an issue that is often disregarded, yet it has a significant effect on the creation of conducive learning environments (Shield & Dockrell, 2003). Globally, noise pollution is a major problem that impacts students' academic performance and general well-being (Stansfeld & Matheson, 2003). A study involving 450 university students found that noise levels were higher for off-campus students, with reading and mental tasks being the most affected. Additionally, rest disturbances positively impacted on-campus students' cumulative GPA. These findings suggest that noise annoyance may influence students' activities and potentially affect their academic performance (Onchang & Hawker, 2018). Therefore, it is essential for educational institutions to fully understand and minimize the global impact of noise pollution to better prepare their students for life in a globalized society.

Notably, sources like surface transportation, particularly road vehicles, contribute extensively to this problem, making vehicular noise a pervasive and challenging issue to control. Noise is not only disrupting activities, instead it disturbs sleep, generates stress, and hinders one's ability to accomplish tasks (Halperin, 2014). According to Wagenaar and Burris (2013) in the Network for Public Health Law, despite extensive research demonstrating the significant health risks associated with noise, some communities have not adequately integrated these risks into their policies. Studies spanning decades, supported by Goines and Hagler (2007) and Passchier-Vermeer and Passchier (2000), have highlighted the profound health effects of noise,

surpassing many other environmental hazards. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) emphasizes that prolonged exposure to noise levels exceeding 70 dB can heighten hypertension symptoms and trigger hostile responses. Cognitive functions like attention, memory, and problem-solving are disrupted by noise, and efforts to ignore it can temporarily help but may elevate stress hormones and blood pressure (Stansfeld & Matheson, 2003). Recent evidence suggests a link between high noise levels, hypertension, and ischaemic heart diseases, highlighting the health implications of noise pollution. The research underscores the need for policy interventions to address noise as a significant environmental hazard, especially in cases of long-term exposure above 70 dB. Prioritizing the mitigation of noise pollution is crucial for public health (Münzel et al., 2014).

Tomek and Urhahne's (2022) study on 178 German student teachers revealed that noise increases stress levels but may initially enhance performance before causing a decline. Using Lazarus' stress model, their experiments indicated both positive and negative effects of noise exposure on tasks like error correction. The findings emphasize the nuanced relationship between noise and stress, highlighting the potential benefits of mitigating classroom noise for teachers' mental health and professional efficiency.

According to the Liceo Journal of Higher Education Research, classrooms and home learning environments in a Western province of the Philippines are highly polluted with loud noises, potentially harming students' cognitive abilities. Students contribute to this pollution, and poor cognitive performances indicate a need for attention to cognitive health. The study emphasizes the negative impact of noise pollution on learning abilities and calls for serious attention, sound limit policies, and

health education programs to address environmental problems in Filipino schools and residential areas (Opiso & Alburoa, 2014). It notes the task performance difficulties and highlights the importance of considering the relatively small sample size due to time constraints, acknowledging its potential impact on the study results for students (Eno et al., 2023).

This reveals a disconnect between students' perception of noise and actual exposure levels, unaffected by demographics. Classroom noise varies by location, and when compared, students' perceived exposure aligns with harmful levels. In Argao, Cebu, Philippines, noise pollution in schools is overlooked, impacting students' well-being and learning. The study recommends an awareness program and classroom design modifications to address this issue, emphasizing the need for noise pollution education and improved acoustics for a healthier learning environment.

At the local level, sources of noise, especially road traffic, pose a primary disturbance. Noise from domestic premises, amplified music, and aircraft further compound this issue, significantly affecting communities (Babisch, 2002). This local context underscores the urgency of a comprehensive evaluation and mitigation of noise pollution within educational spaces, specifically at CTU Moalboal. This study aims to thoroughly evaluate noise pollution in the educational spaces at CTU Moalboal by assessing the following key components: the profiles of each classroom, including room placement, equipment, and fixtures, as well as the current sound level intensity in each classroom on the 4th floor of the New Administration Building. The investigation will identify which classroom exhibits the highest sound level intensity and analyze whether there is a significant relationship between the sound levels inside the classrooms and those outside. By offering broadly applicable insights, this study hopes to promote an environment that is conducive to learning on a global scale.

Theoretical Background

This study is anchored in the environmental psychology theory by Moser and Uzzell (2003). Environmental psychology provides a compelling lens through which to examine the intricate relationship between noise pollution and human behavior. Their insights reveal that emotional responses, such as anxiety and frustration, are significantly triggered by environmental stressors like excessive noise. This emotional turmoil can lead to disengagement from community initiatives aimed at addressing these challenges, as individuals may feel overwhelmed by their environment. However, when people become aware of how noise pollution affects their health and well-being, particularly its impact on sleep and cognitive function, they often develop a deeper emotional connection to their surroundings. This realization can transform fear into proactive engagement, motivating individuals to advocate for noise reduction strategies in their communities.

Furthermore, the theory highlights the importance of place attachment and social cohesion in fostering a collective response to noise pollution. When residents feel a strong connection to their neighborhood, they are more likely to unite in addressing environmental issues that disrupt their sense of place. Initiatives designed to promote community pride, such as the creation of quiet zones or green spaces, can strengthen social ties and encourage stewardship behaviors. By prioritizing these psychological elements, interventions can be more effective in combating noise pollution, ultimately enhancing the collective well-being of the community. Moser and Uzzell's framework emphasize that addressing noise pollution is not only about technical solutions but also about recognizing and harnessing the emotional and social undercurrents that drive human behaviour, paving the way for innovative, community-focused policies that protect public health (Moser & Uzzell, 2003).

Psychological Impact of Noise Pollution

Noise pollution affects mental health by increasing stress levels and contributing to mood disorders. Research by Moser and Uzzell (2003) indicates that emotional reactions such as fear, anger, or frustration, which are associated with environmental changes, can alter behavior and lead to avoidance strategies. This principle applies to noise pollution, where continuous exposure to loud or disruptive sounds can trigger anxiety and irritability. Individuals who live in noisy environments often report feeling overwhelmed, which leads to a decrease in overall well-being (Moser & Uzzell, 2003). Additionally, Stansfeld and Matheson (2003) highlight that prolonged exposure to environmental noise can result in elevated stress levels, which in turn can contribute to the development of mood disorders such as anxiety and depression.

Awareness and Emotional Responses

Moser and Uzzell highlight the role of emotional awareness in motivating pro-environmental action. In the context of noise pollution, raising awareness about the negative health impacts of excessive noise can foster emotional connections that stimulate proactive measures. For instance, individuals who recognize the detrimental effects of noise on sleep and cognitive function might be more inclined to advocate for noise reduction strategies in their communities (Moser & Uzzell, 2003).

Cognitive Performance

The study "The Effect of Noise Exposure on Cognitive Performance and Brain Activity," conducted by Jafari et al. (2019), investigates how different levels of noise exposure impact cognitive functions such as attention and mental workload. Involving 54 participants, the researchers utilized data loggers to monitor EEG

(electroencephalogram) signals while subjects performed cognitive tasks under varying noise levels of 75, 85, and 95 decibels (dBA). The findings revealed that exposure to 95 dBA significantly impaired both visual and auditory attention, highlighting the cognitive challenges posed by excessive noise. Additionally, changes in brain activity were noted, with an increase in alpha wave power and a decrease in beta wave power, indicating disruptions in cognitive processing. This study underscores the critical implications of noise pollution on cognitive health, suggesting a need for practical interventions to mitigate noise in environments where concentration is essential.

Sound Level Intensity

Sound level intensity refers to the measure of the loudness of sound as it propagates through a medium, such as air. It is defined mathematically as the power (P) of the sound wave divided by the area (A) over which that power is distributed:

$$I = \frac{P}{A}$$

Where I , represent the sound intensity in watts per square meter. In practical terms, this measurement provides an objective quantification of sound, allowing researchers and engineers to assess the loudness of various noises in different environments.

Data Logger

According to Zhao et al. (2017), the use of sound level data loggers in educational settings allows for precise monitoring of noise pollution levels, offering valuable insights into how varying sound intensities can affect learning environments. Such monitoring plays a crucial role in understanding acoustic conditions and

implementing effective noise management strategies to enhance overall educational experiences.

Three sound level data loggers were utilized to measure and analyze noise intensity across various locations in the fourth-floor classrooms of the new administration building at CTU Moalboal Campus, specifically focusing on unoccupied classrooms and hallways. The first data logger, named ESP02, was strategically placed in the hallway to capture ambient noise levels during periods when the space was empty, providing insights into how the acoustics of the hallway might be influenced by external conditions. The second data logger, designated as ESP04, was positioned inside one of the unoccupied classrooms, each equipped with an air conditioning unit, to monitor sound levels in an environment devoid of human activity while also accounting for the impact of mechanical noise generated by the air conditioning systems. Finally, the third data logger, referred to as ESP01, was situated outside the building, adjacent to the highway, to evaluate the influence of external noise sources on the acoustic environment of the new administration building. This careful arrangement of data loggers facilitated the collection of a comprehensive dataset that highlights the interactions between internal and external noise factors.

By prioritizing these actions, the plan aims to transform emotional awareness into community-driven advocacy for noise reduction strategies, ultimately enhancing the acoustic environment and supporting the overall well-being of the campus community. Regular assessments using data loggers will continue to monitor the effectiveness of these interventions, ensuring that the proposed strategies adapt to evolving needs and effectively contribute to a quieter, more focused educational atmosphere.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Sound Level Intensity in Classrooms

Research on sound level intensity in classrooms has found that noise significantly impacts students' learning, attention, and classroom dynamics. In a study conducted by Bistafa and Bradley (2000), it was suggested that a minimum signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of 15 dB is necessary for classrooms. However, later studies showed that younger students require even higher SNRs to perform at comparable levels to older students (Shojaei et al., 2016). For instance, Xie et al. (2011) indicated in their study that persistent low SNR conditions correlate negatively with speech intelligibility and cognitive performance, thereby underscoring the importance of maintaining adequate sound levels for effective learning.

Another investigation by Astolfi et al. (2019) measured the ambient noise levels in K–12 classrooms and found that background noise could reach levels as high as 75 dBA during active student engagement. The study revealed that classroom speech levels often exceeded 65 dBA for 35% of the school day. Moreover, conditions associated with lower SNR correlated with increased vocal effort and fatigue experienced by teachers, which could impede their teaching effectiveness (Brill & Wang, 2021). Overall, addressing the acoustic environment by adhering to recommended standards, such as those set by ANSI S12.60, can greatly enhance the educational experience by fostering a more conducive learning atmosphere. Adjustments in classroom design, implementation of sound systems, and sound-absorbing materials can help mitigate the adverse effects of noise in educational settings.

Room Placement and Design

Room placement plays a crucial role in managing noise levels, significantly affecting comfort and productivity in various settings, especially in educational and occupational environments. A study by Barrett et al. (2019) demonstrates how room orientation and placement relative to noise sources such as busy streets or industrial areas can influence acoustic quality. The authors emphasize that classrooms situated away from external noise sources exhibit lower ambient noise levels, thus enhancing students' ability to concentrate and engage in learning activities. This research provides compelling evidence that thoughtful room placement can lead to improved auditory environments, particularly in urban settings where noise pollution is prevalent.

Moreover, research by Mateus et al. (2017) highlights the significance of room design and placement within buildings to mitigate sound transmission. Their findings indicate that classrooms located in the central areas of educational facilities tend to have better acoustic insulation and less exposure to ambient noise from outdoors compared to those situated near external walls. The study further discusses incorporating sound-absorbing materials and strategic layouts to minimize noise from adjacent rooms and hallways. Collectively, these studies underline the importance of considering room placement and design in noise management strategies to enhance learning environments and overall comfort in various spaces.

Room Equipment and Fixtures

The influence of room equipment and fixtures on acoustic quality and noise levels has become a significant area of research in recent years, especially in educational and workplace settings. A study by Bhandari et al. (2024) examined how different types of classroom furniture, such as desks, chairs, and acoustic panels, affect sound distribution and absorption. The authors found that fixtures designed with

sound-absorbing materials significantly reduced noise reverberation, thereby improving speech intelligibility among students and facilitating a better learning environment. This research highlights that the choice of equipment and fixtures directly impacts auditory clarity, emphasizing the need for thoughtfully designed classroom furnishings to enhance educational outcomes.

Furthermore, research by Chintapalli (2024) illustrates the effects of room fixtures on acoustic performance in workplaces. The author reported that the installation of sound-absorbing partitions and strategically placed furniture significantly decreased noise transmission within open-plan setups, thereby improving employee focus and productivity. The findings suggest that fixtures serve not only functional purposes but also play a critical role in noise management. By optimizing room equipment and fixtures, organizations can create environments conducive to concentration and collaboration, demonstrating the importance of acoustically informed design in various settings.

Noise Pollution Evaluation

The assessment of noise pollution in educational settings, such as the CTU Moalboal New Administration Building classrooms, involves a multifaceted approach. Anjum and Kumari (2022) highlight the significance of measuring average noise levels, employing methods like the equivalent sound pressure level (LAeq). Mas' idah and Marlyana (2022) emphasize the creation of noise maps to visualize the spatial distribution of noise. The inclusion of psychoacoustic metrics, as discussed by Jagniatinskis et al. (2017), adds a subjective dimension, considering frequency characteristics and individual perceptions. Short-term measurements, suggested by Marinov et al. (2016), are deemed valuable when long-term monitoring faces

limitations, provided they adhere to representative conditions. Overall, a comprehensive evaluation of noise pollution integrates objective measurements like LAeq with subjective assessments based on psychoacoustic parameters, as emphasized by Soeta et al. (2015).

Several studies have delved into the assessment of noise pollution, shedding light on its diverse impacts. For instance, Kasagici and Ateş (2021) investigated noise pollution in various settings within a Turkish city, uncovering excessive noise levels in schools and hospitals, violating regulation limits. In India, Roy et al. (2022) conducted a study across three semiurban towns, highlighting elevated noise levels in commercial and heavy traffic areas. Subramaniam et al. (2019) focused on Malaysia, assessing noise exposure in the manufacturing industry and identifying a heightened risk of noise-induced hearing loss among workers. Lastly, de Souza et al. (2020) explored the impact of sound pressure on user perception and behaviour in a Brazilian university campus, finding that a majority of measurements, both outdoor and indoor, exceeded recommended limits. These studies collectively contribute valuable insights to the broader understanding of noise pollution assessment.

Osei (2023) investigated the awareness of basic school teachers in Ghana regarding noise pollution and proposed control measures. In Texas, Chakraborty and Aun (2023) examined social inequities in exposure to traffic-related air and noise pollution, revealing disparities in schools serving minority and socioeconomically deprived students. Chahdi et al. (2021) conducted a review analysing articles from South Africa and China, presenting diverse solutions to address noise pollution in school environments. A study in Jao Monlevade, Brazil by de Castro et al. (2019) evaluated acoustic conditions in classrooms, finding sound pressure levels above recommended standards. Additionally, Nedojedlá et al. (2018) measured A-weighted

sound pressure levels in primary school classrooms, revealing the negative impact of school noise on information processing and communication. These studies collectively contribute to understanding and addressing noise pollution in educational settings, offering insights and potential solutions for mitigating its adverse effects.

Identification of Sources

Many studies have delved into the assessment of noise pollution in educational settings, particularly in external areas. Amoatey et al. (2023) conducted a study evaluating the sonic, acoustic, and overall environment of external areas in kindergartens, primary, and secondary schools in Rome, Florence, and Perugia. Busa et al. (2022) explored sound levels across different school areas and times, discovering values surpassing permissible levels set by the Malaysian Department of Environment. Furthermore, Chahdi et al. (2021) investigated infrasound and low-frequency noise occurrence in classrooms and surrounding areas of a primary school, comparing the findings with other nearby schools. These collective studies offer valuable insights into the origins and intensities of noise pollution in school external areas, contributing to the identification and comprehension of this prevalent issue.

The review of related literature highlights various methods for identifying and assessing noise pollution. Traditional analysis, signal processing, and modern spectrum estimation are commonly employed to analyse noise sources and reduce overall noise levels (Jhanwar, 2016). Digital signal processing and spectrum estimation have proven effective in identifying noise sources in engineering machinery. Additionally, techniques like sound intensity measurement, acoustic holography, and beamforming have been developed for noise source identification, contributing significantly to noise control and signal source identification (Yang et al.,

2009). These methodologies provide a comprehensive foundation for assessing noise pollution in educational settings, such as the CTU Moalboal New Administration Building Classrooms.

Jhanwar (2016) proposes a method combining sound pressure and sound intensity techniques for accurate identification of environmental noise sources. Chang et al. (2014) utilizes a priority risk index (NCPI) to evaluate and select critical units for implementing noise control measures in industrial settings. Nassiri et al. (2013) introduces a method based on partial coherence analysis and analytic hierarchy process for sorting noise source contributions in multi-source excitation systems. Additionally, Wu et al. (2013) emphasize spatial localization of noise sources through a combination of sound source localization and noise separation methods, aiding in the identification and treatment of underlying components contributing to a source. These approaches offer valuable tools for minimizing worker exposure and implementing appropriate control measures in the context of noise pollution assessment in CTU Moalboal New Administration Building classrooms.

Implementation Strategies

Green living systems like green roofs and vertical greening have emerged as sustainable solutions to enhance environmental balance and alleviate noise pollution (Houghtaling et al., 2023). The surface acoustical characteristics of buildings, including facades and surfaces, significantly impact noise propagation in urban environments. Research by Dimitrijević et al. (2017) emphasizes the role of increasing surface absorption through outdoor design, incorporating elements like green areas and porous asphalt to reduce sound levels near building facades. The amalgamation of

these approaches, coupled with perception-based methods and acoustic design, holds promise in enhancing the quality of life in urban areas.

The literature reveals a growing concern regarding noise pollution in educational settings. A study of Bulunuz et al. (2022), emphasize its negative impact on primary school students, highlighting the need for effective strategies. ÇETİN and HAMEDOĞLU's (2022) research underscores the oversight of noise control measures by school administrators. International perspectives from South Africa and China, as seen in Chahdi et al. (2021), contribute diverse insights into addressing noise pollution in schools. Md Norzeri and Jamaludin's (2018) study highlights elevated noise levels in school surroundings, emphasizing the urgency for conducive learning environments. This body of literature establishes the global significance of addressing noise pollution in educational institutions.

Mobile crowd sensing (MCS) using smartphones, as highlighted by Parvan et al. (2021), offers real-time monitoring and analysis of noise parameters, incorporating location and temporal data. Civic engagement, as advocated by Bi et al. (2016), involves providing residents with information, encouraging participation in policymaking, and fostering advocacy skills. Improved communication between residents and municipal organizations is crucial (Wills, 2001), with technology playing a role in facilitating coordinated actions and mediating data quality assessments (Muratori et al., 2011). Collectively, these strategies empower communities to actively engage in noise pollution control and ensure accountability from authorities (Moses & Excell, 2020).

Impact on Learning

The existing literature on noise pollution and its effects on health outcomes, with a focus on learning environments, has been thoroughly examined. Stansfeld and Matheson (2003) underscore the intricate connection between individual perceptions of environmental noise and its impact on health, emphasizing the influence on learning. The identified reactions to noise, including annoyance, disruptive sleep, and cognitive performance, are intricately linked to the perceived quality of life. Notably, active strategies employed by individuals to manage or avoid noise could potentially mitigate its adverse effects, underscoring a crucial aspect in this complex relationship. Despite these insights, there is a recognized need for further research employing refined measurement techniques and longitudinal studies to comprehensively understand how noise perception influences health outcomes, particularly in the context of learning and cognitive impacts.

The study by Ryherd et al. (2012) significantly contributes to the understanding of noise pollution's impact on student performance, shedding light on a critical but understudied aspect amid increasing noise levels in urban areas. By examining empirical data from major Indian cities and correlating it with academic metrics, the research reveals a gender-specific influence, with Class 12 boys experiencing a 6.1 percent rise in failure rates for every ten percentage-point increase in noisy days during the January-March quarter. Intriguingly, this effect is concentrated during examination periods, emphasizing the importance of timing in assessing noise pollution's repercussions. The proximity to noise monitoring stations further magnifies the relationship, particularly in schools within 1 km, where a similar rise in noisy days amplifies failure rates among boys by 11.3 percent. The study delves into potential mechanisms, proposing that noise pollution adversely affects attention, particularly

under heightened cognitive demands during examinations. This empirical evidence underscores the need for a comprehensive investigation into noise pollution's impact on student performance in specific contexts, such as the new administration building classrooms at CTU Moalboal.

Numerous studies, drawing from various academic databases and search engines, extensively examine the ramifications of noise pollution on patients within hospital settings. These investigations highlight the adverse effects of noise on patient well-being, particularly in disrupting sleep patterns, eliciting physiological stress responses, prolonging hospital stays, impacting pain management, and potentially hindering wound healing processes. Despite a prevailing consensus regarding the detrimental impact of noise on patients, conflicting findings exist within the literature, presenting inconclusive outcomes in certain cases. Notably, the review underscores the limited exploration of specific acoustic metrics and intervention methodologies, indicating a critical need for further research to comprehend and mitigate the disruptive effects of hospital noise on patient outcomes and overall well-being (Adbi and Ghosh, 2023).

Limited research has been conducted on noise pollution within educational settings, with a particular focus on new administration buildings and classrooms. Although ample literature exists on noise's impact in healthcare environments, the exploration of its effects in academic institutions, such as CTU Moalboal, is notably scarce. Understanding the specific acoustic metrics relevant to classrooms and implementing effective intervention strategies are critical gaps in the existing research. This review emphasizes the need for comprehensive investigations into the noise levels within CTU Moalboal's new administration building classrooms, shedding light on potential disruptions to student concentration, academic performance, and overall

well-being. Addressing these gaps will contribute valuable insights to the broader discourse on noise pollution and its implications for educational environments.

Guidelines and Recommendations

In the domain of Design Standards, the discussion around traffic noise modelling, assessment methodologies, and the essential update of guidelines finds a significant resonance. The understanding of predictive models developed from traffic parameters and environmental factors is crucial before their integration into local contexts. Findings from the examination of global models illustrate a prevalent trend where nations adapt existing frameworks, emphasizing multi-tiered noise reduction strategies within transportation systems. This analysis underscores the urgency of revising outdated noise guidelines, prompted by shifting urban dynamics, burgeoning populations, and escalating vehicular activity. Additionally, it emphasizes the crucial need to incorporate noise assessments during road construction and maintenance phases to ensure the development of sustainable infrastructure. However, a notable gap lies within the outdated guidelines that fail to address contemporary challenges, necessitating their revision to align with the evolving landscape of urbanization and vehicular density (Ibili et al., 2022).

Despite the substantial scientific knowledge available for urban sound planning, there's a clear gap in effectively disseminating these findings to policymakers and local authorities. This knowledge deficit significantly impacts the implementation of noise pollution policies. The lower completeness level in subsequent noise mapping rounds indicates a lack of efficient utilization of research outcomes by planners and decision-makers. Bridging this gap requires enhanced communication strategies to better integrate research findings into practical policy frameworks. Such efforts aim to align

defined objectives with tangible outcomes in reducing noise pollution within European urban areas (Alves et al., 2016).

Agreements and Disagreements in the Literature

Agreements in the literature generally aligns on the detrimental effects of noise pollution on various aspects, including health, learning, and well-being. There's consensus on the need for effective evaluation methods, source identification, and implementation strategies to mitigate noise pollution. On the other hand, the disagreements in the literature discrepancies exist regarding specific methodologies for noise evaluation, identification of sources, and the effectiveness of certain control strategies. Additionally, while many studies agree on the adverse impact of noise, there might be variations in the degree or extent of its effects across different contexts or populations.

In conclusion, the comprehensive exploration of noise pollution in the literature has revealed its profound negative impact on various facets of our lives, affecting health, learning environments, patient well-being, and overall quality of life. What stands out prominently is the necessity for employing robust evaluation techniques such as psychoacoustic metrics, noise mapping, and diverse source identification methods as fundamental pillars for devising effective noise control measures. The literature strongly emphasizes the urgency of updating guidelines and policies, emphasizing their adaptation to the constantly evolving urban landscape, as indispensable measures to comprehensively tackle the pervasive issue of noise pollution.

Our research focuses on advancing noise pollution evaluation methods by combining machine learning techniques for source identification in urban

environments. It aims to bridge gaps in current methodologies by proposing a hybrid approach that integrates multiple data sources for more accurate noise source identification and mapping. This research seeks to contribute to the ongoing efforts in developing more precise and effective strategies for noise pollution control and mitigation, aligning with the existing literature's emphasis on improved evaluation and source identification techniques.

Figure 2. Literature Map

THE PROBLEM

Statement of the Problem

The study focuses on assessing noise pollution specifically within CTU Moalboal's New Administration Building 4th Floor Classrooms. The researchers will measure the sound level intensity in each classroom and identify which classroom has the highest sound level intensity. Additionally, it will examine whether there is a significant relationship between sound levels inside the classrooms and those outside. Based on the findings, the research will provide possible recommendations to address noise pollution and enhance the educational environment within this specific building.

Precisely will answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of each classroom based on the following:
 - A. Room Placement;
 - B. Equipment and Fixtures?
2. What is the sound level intensity in each Classroom in 4th floor New Admin Building?
3. Which classroom has the highest sound level intensity?
4. Is there a significant relationship of Sound Level between inside and outside of classroom?
5. What are the possible recommendations?

Significance of the Study

This study benefits the following:

Students. This study plays a crucial role in enhancing students' understanding of how noise pollution affects their concentration and learning abilities. By presenting empirical data on sound levels in classrooms, it informs students of the potential barriers they face in their academic environment. As they become aware of these challenges, students can advocate for noise reduction measures that could lead to more conducive learning conditions. Furthermore, the study provides students with practical experience in applying research methodologies, fostering their research skills, and preparing them for future academic endeavors. This engagement promotes a culture of active learning, where students take initiative in understanding and improving their educational environment.

Teachers. For educators, this study offers invaluable insights into the detrimental effects of noise on student learning and engagement. It highlights how excessive noise can hinder effective teaching by distracting students and impeding their ability to absorb information. By understanding these impacts, teachers can modify their instructional strategies to mitigate the adverse effects of noise, ultimately enhancing student participation and academic performance. The findings may motivate teachers to collaborate with school administrators to advocate for necessary changes, such as acoustic improvements within classrooms, which can transform the learning experience for their students.

Parents. The study raises awareness among parents regarding the critical influence of noise on their children's educational outcomes. By understanding how noise can impact learning, parents can support initiatives aimed at reducing classroom

noise and advocate for their children's needs within the school environment. This increasing awareness empowers parents to engage in discussions with school officials about potential noise mitigation strategies and to support community efforts that seek to create quieter learning spaces. Additionally, it encourages parents to take steps at home to minimize distractions, thereby fostering a more supportive educational atmosphere.

Community. On a broader scale, this study serves to inform the community about the significant impacts of noise pollution on education and overall well-being. By understanding the sources and levels of noise affecting local schools, community members can engage in advocacy for noise control measures, such as urban planning initiatives that prioritize quiet zones around educational institutions. The insights gained from this research enable local authorities and residents to collaborate in creating a more peaceful environment that benefits both students and residents. Ultimately, this collective awareness promotes a community culture that prioritizes the health and educational needs of its youth.

Future Researchers. This study establishes a foundational understanding of the relationship between noise pollution and academic performance, serving as a valuable resource for future researchers. It opens avenues for further exploration into specific noise reduction strategies and their effectiveness in improving educational outcomes. Additionally, it provides data and insights that can contribute to the broader scientific discourse surrounding environmental factors influencing learning. Future research can build on the findings of this study by examining different variables, such as the effectiveness of various acoustic treatments in different learning environments, thus enhancing the body of knowledge on this critical subject.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section of the study introduces the research methodology. It includes the research method, the research flow of the study, the research environment, the research instrument, the data gathering procedure, statistical treatment, and the definition of terms.

Method

In conducting this study, a quantitative methodological approach will be adopted to understand noise pollution in the New Administration Building at Cebu Technological University - Moalboal. Specifically, this research design aims to quantitatively assess sound level intensity (in decibels) within the 4th-floor classrooms of the New Administration Building at CTU Moalboal using an ESP32 microcontroller as a data logger. The study will involve several key components to systematically measure and analyze the sound levels to understand the classroom environment better.

Research Flow of the Study

The key stages in this research involve firstly identifying the issue of noise pollution within the new level admin building of CTU Moalboal. Following this, a comprehensive literature review will be conducted to understand existing knowledge and identify gaps in noise pollution studies relevant to educational environments. Once the methodology is set, data collection will be executed, employing various methods such as using ESP32 microcontroller as a data logger and observations. The collected data will then undergo meticulous analysis using statistical tools and qualitative methods to derive meaningful conclusions and present findings aligned with the

research objectives. This logical sequence portrays the progression of the research from the initial identification of the problem to the ultimate presentation of findings.

Figure 3. Research Flow of The Study

RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT

The study was conducted at Cebu Technological University-Moalboal Campus, specifically focusing on the 4th floor of the New Administration Building. This floor consists of four classrooms: Room 01, Room 02, Room 03, and Room 05, each measuring approximately 8 meters in width and 3.5 meters in height. These uniform dimensions allow for a consistent comparative analysis of how various factors influence noise levels within each classroom. With an average of 30 students utilizing each classroom during class hours, this setting provides a dynamic environment where noise levels may fluctuate based on student interaction, teaching methods, and external disturbances.

The New Administration Building is an ideal setting for this study due to its architectural layout and proximity to potential noise sources. The building is located near roadways and communal areas and has a hallway that causes the classrooms to experience varying noise levels, which directly affect the educational experience. The exposure to external noise reflects real-world conditions faced by students, making the research both relevant and practical. These fluctuating noise levels provide an opportunity to study whether outside noise can impact the acoustics inside the classrooms.

Understanding how these noise levels affect classroom dynamics will allow for a more comprehensive analysis of the role of acoustics in student performance and provide insights for improving the learning environment.

CTU-MOALBOAL NEW ADMINISTRATION BUILDING

Figure 4. Research Environment

Instruments

The instruments will be employed to gather comprehensive data on noise pollution within CTU Moalboal's New Administration Building. Objective measurements of noise levels will be obtained using an ESP32 microcontroller as a data logger, which will be strategically placed inside and outside selected classrooms. This device will enable accurate monitoring of sound levels in real-time.

Figure 5: ESP32 microcontroller (ESP01, ESP02, and ESP04)

Data Gathering Procedures

The data gathering process will commence with the placement of the data logger outside and inside selected classrooms on the 4th floor of CTU Moalboal's New Administration Building to measure noise levels objectively. The fourth floor consists of four classrooms: ROOM 01, ROOM 02, ROOM 03, and ROOM 05. Thirty observations per location will be conducted, including areas outside the classrooms near the roadside, the hallway, and inside each classroom. The data will be gathered simultaneously within five-minute intervals to ensure comprehensive and accurate measurements.

Statistical Treatment

The data is analysed using One-way ANOVA test to identify which classroom has the highest sound level intensity and Pearson's Correlation Coefficient to examine the relationship between the inside and outside noise levels.

A One-way ANOVA test will be employed to identify which classroom has the highest sound level intensity. This statistical method allows for comparison of the average sound levels across the different classrooms, enabling the researchers to determine which specific environment exhibits the most significant noise pollution. If the results of the One-way ANOVA test indicate a significant difference, a post hoc test will be conducted to determine which specific classrooms differ significantly from each other. The post hoc analysis will provide further insights into the specific pairs of classrooms with the most substantial differences in sound level intensity. The formula below represents the one-way ANOVA test statistics.

Table 1: One-way ANOVA Formula

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares (MS)	F
Within	$SSW = \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{i=1}^l (X - \bar{X}_j)^2$	$df_w = k - 1$	$MSW = \frac{SSW}{df_w}$	$F = \frac{MSB}{MSW}$
Between	$SSB = \sum_{j=1}^k (\bar{X}_j - \bar{X})^2$	$df_b = n - k$	$MSB = \frac{SSB}{df_b}$	
Total	$SST = \sum_{j=1}^n (\bar{X}_j - \bar{X})^2$	$df_t = n - 1$		

Following this analysis, Pearson's Correlation Coefficient will be used to examine the relationship between the inside and outside noise levels, providing additional insights into how external noise may impact the classroom environment. Correlation coefficients, which range from -1 to +1, reflect the strength and direction of a linear relationship.

The formula for Pearson's correlation is;

$$r = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

r = correlation coefficient

x_i = values of the x-variable in a sample

\bar{x} = mean of the values of the x-variable

y_i = values of the y-variable in a sample

\bar{y} = mean of the values of the y-variable

Definition of Terms

To be more understand the terminologies used in this study, the following expressions are discussed and clarified in the context of this research.

Noise Pollution - is defined as the presence of harmful or excessive sound levels that disrupt normal activities, such as sleeping, conversation, and learning. This term encompasses a variety of noise sources, including transportation and everyday human activities that emit unwanted sound. The study examines how noise pollution influences educational environments, emphasizing the need for effective management strategies in classrooms.

Conducive Learning Environments - refer to educational settings designed to foster learning by minimizing distractions and enhancing focus. These environments are characterized by optimal lighting, cleanliness, and, importantly, appropriate acoustic conditions. The study aims to explore how noise pollution compromises these conditions, ultimately affecting students' learning outcomes.

Sound Level Intensity - refers to the quantitative measure of sound's loudness as it traverses through a medium, expressed in decibels (dB). This measurement provides an objective means to assess noise levels in classrooms. The research employs sound level intensity data to understand the acoustic landscape within the building and its potential effects on students' academic performance.

Data Logger - is an electronic device used to continuously monitor and record specific environmental parameters, such as noise levels over time. In this study, an ESP32 microcontroller serves as a data logger, strategically placed inside and outside classrooms to capture real-time sound intensity data. This technology enables precise assessments of how noise pollution varies in different educational settings.

Room placement - discusses the strategic arrangement of classrooms within a building, which significantly influences the exposure to noise pollution from both internal and external sources. This study examines how the location of each classroom relative to busy roadways and communal areas affects sound levels and, consequently, the quality of the learning environment.

Equipment and fixtures - encompass the movable and fixed items in classroom settings, such as desks, chairs, and acoustic panels, which can influence the acoustic quality and noise levels. The study evaluates how different types of equipment and fixtures either contribute to or alleviate noise issues, considering their design and materials in relation to sound absorption.

Identification of Sources - involves analysing the specific origins of noise pollution affecting educational spaces. This includes evaluating external disturbances, such as vehicular traffic and construction noise, as well as internal factors like classroom activities and equipment. Understanding these sources is crucial for developing targeted noise mitigation strategies.

Implementation Strategies - refer to the methods and actions taken to address and reduce noise pollution within educational environments. In this study, strategies may include recommendations for classroom design modifications, sound-absorbing materials, and creating policies aimed at managing noise levels effectively to enhance the learning experience.

Impact on Learning - pertains to the observable effects that noise pollution has on students' cognitive abilities, emotional well-being, and overall academic performance. The research investigates how high noise levels correlate with

decreased concentration, increased stress, and diminished academic outcomes, highlighting the need for prioritizing noise reduction in educational spaces.

Guidelines and Recommendations - signify the formal suggestions derived from the study's findings aimed at mitigating noise pollution. These may include proposed maximum allowable noise levels, suggested improvements for classroom acoustics, and the integration of noise management practices into educational policies to foster a better learning environment.

CHAPTER 2

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents analysis, interpretation, and assessments of the data gathered within CTU Moalboal's New Administration Building 4th Floor Classrooms. The data are statistically analyzed to bring about the necessary results.

Profiles of Classrooms Based on Room Placement and the Type of Equipment and Fixtures

This section provides the profile of each classroom in 4th floor New Administration Building, in terms of their placement and their equipment and fixtures. All classrooms have equal dimensions, with an estimated size of 8 meters in length, 7 meters in width, and 3.5 meters in height. The study profiles each classroom by examining their specific room placements and the types of equipment and fixtures present. This analysis is crucial for understanding how noise travels within the classroom environment. Examining room placement and the types of equipment and fixtures can provide valuable insights into sound propagation and its impact on the learning experience (Massonnié et al., 2019).

Figure 6: Front View of Each Classroom

Figure 7: Top View of Each Classrooms

Figure 8: 3D Illustration of Each Classrooms

Table 2: The Room Placement of Each Classroom on the 4TH Floor of The New Administration Building

Classrooms	Room Placement
ROOM 01	Located facing southwest, on the left side of the building near the Research and Graduate School Building. A hallway runs in front of the classroom, and the back of the room is near the roadside.
ROOM 02	Positioned facing southwest, directly beside Room 01. It also has a hallway in front, with the back of the room near the roadside.
ROOM 03	Facing southwest, situated between Room 02 and the faculty room. Like the other rooms, it has a hallway in front, and the back is near the roadside.
ROOM 05	Facing southwest, located beside the comfort room on the right side of the building. This room also features a hallway in front, with the back near the roadside and close to the entrance and exit of the campus.

The table above shows the placement of each classroom (ROOM 01, ROOM 02, ROOM 03, and ROOM 05). Each room is located on the 4th floor of the CTU Moalboal New Administration Building. It is a four-story building and has an estimated height of 20 meters. Research indicates that noise levels can vary significantly based on building height and proximity to noise sources. A study by Shield and Dockrell (2008) examined the impact of environmental noise on classroom environments and found that excessive noise, even at higher elevations, can disrupt student

concentration and reduce speech intelligibility. Their research highlights that while higher floors may experience reduced noise levels from ground-level sources like traffic, reflective surfaces from nearby buildings or open areas can direct sound upward, potentially affecting classrooms on elevated floors.

Table 3: The Equipment and Fixtures in Each Classroom

Equipment and Fixtures	QUANTITY			
	ROOM 01	ROOM 02	ROOM 03	ROOM 05
CEILING FAN	4	4	4	4
SMART TV	1	1	1	1
COMPUTER	2	0	3	3
AIRCON	2	1	2	1
CURTAINS	6	6	6	6
CABINET	0	1	1	0
DESK	1	1	1	1
CHAIRS	33	30	34	35
INSULATION FOAM	-	-	Installed in every window with a thickness of 1 cm	-

The table above lists the equipment and fixtures in the classrooms of the CTU Moalboal New Administration Building on the 4th floor. Each room is equipped with various fixtures and equipment that influence noise levels within the learning environment.

Ceiling Fans

Each room (01, 02, 03, 05) has 4 ceiling fans. Ceiling fans contribute to the overall noise environment through the operation of their motors and the movement of air. Depending on the fan's design, speed, and maintenance, they can produce low-frequency noise, which can be distracting. Pellegatti et al. (2023) noted that ceiling fans, while useful for air circulation, can interfere with speech intelligibility and contribute to background noise, potentially hindering communication in a classroom.

Smart TVs

Each classroom (01, 02, 03, 05) has one smart TV. These TVs can contribute to the noise in the room, particularly when used for presentations or playing videos with sound. Park et al. (2013) found that televisions, when used at high volumes, can add significant noise to the classroom, making it harder for students to focus and impacting teachers' ability to communicate effectively.

Computers

Room 01 has 2 computers, Room 02 has none, Room 03 has 3, and Room 05 has 3. Computers generate noise from their internal fans, cooling systems, and hard drives. The noise they emit can be distracting, especially when several computers are used simultaneously. Smart et al. (2022) found that electronic devices like computers can increase background noise levels in classrooms, potentially affecting concentration and reducing the clarity of speech.

Window Air Conditioners

Each room (Room 01, Room 02, Room 03, and Room 05) is equipped with 2 window air conditioners. Window air conditioners contribute to noise due to the operation of their compressors and fan motors. This type of air conditioner produces both low-frequency hums and higher-pitched noise, which can interfere with speech intelligibility and disrupt learning. Karami et al. (2017) noted that window air conditioners are especially noisy because their units are often installed in windows, where their sound is not easily absorbed. This noise can be particularly disruptive in classrooms, affecting focus and communication.

Curtains

Each room (01, 02, 03, 05) has 6 curtains. Curtains help reduce noise by absorbing sound and preventing excessive reverberation within the room. Pieren et al. (2018) in their study found that textile curtains are effective in reducing sound levels, particularly when they are made from materials with high sound-absorbing properties, such as thick cotton, velvet, or polyester blends. The study recommended using curtains with a thickness of at least 1.5 mm for optimal sound absorption. These materials help minimize sound reflections, especially in environments like classrooms, where noise reduction is essential. The appropriate combination of textile type and thickness contributes to creating a quieter and more focused learning atmosphere by minimizing external noise and enhancing speech clarity.

Cabinets

Room 01 and Room 05 do not have cabinets, while Room 02 and Room 03 each have 1 cabinet. Cabinets generally contribute minimally to noise but can influence classroom acoustics depending on their design and the materials inside. Lee

et al. (2013) found that cabinets can generate frictional impulse noise when doors or drawers are opened or closed, particularly if the materials or joints are not properly designed. This noise can add to the overall sound level in a classroom, although its impact is typically smaller compared to other sources. Properly designed cabinets with smooth hinges and padded interiors can help minimize this frictional noise and reduce its impact on the classroom environment.

Desk

Each room (01, 02, 03, 05) contains one desk. Desks themselves do not typically contribute significant noise, but their placement and material can impact classroom acoustics. According to Wenmaekers & van Hout (2019), the design and arrangement of furniture, including desks, can influence the level of reverberation and overall noise in a room. Desks with reflective surfaces can contribute to sound bouncing off them, increasing the room's reverberation time and potentially making it harder for students to understand speech. Conversely, desks made from materials that absorb sound, such as wood or composite materials with soft finishes, can help reduce reverberation and improve speech clarity, creating a more conducive learning environment.

Chairs

Room 01 has 33 chairs, Room 02 has 30, Room 03 has 34, and Room 05 has 35. Chairs can be a major source of noise, especially when they are moved or scraped across the floor. Sala & Rantala (2016) identified chair movement as a significant contributor to classroom noise. The sound of chairs scraping, particularly in classrooms with hard floors, can distract students and make it difficult for teachers to

maintain focus. The large number of chairs in each room increases the potential for noise, especially when students shift positions or engage in group activities.

Insulation Foam

Room 03 has insulation foam installed in every window, with a thickness of 1 cm. The foam helps reduce external noise by absorbing sound and reducing reverberation within the room. According to Mohammadi et al. (2023) foam materials are effective at reducing sound transmission and improving the acoustics of indoor spaces. The study recommends using foam insulation with a thickness of 2 to 3 cm for optimal soundproofing performance. While 1 cm of foam can still provide some noise reduction, particularly for higher-frequency sounds, it may not be as effective at blocking lower-frequency noise or providing substantial soundproofing. This thinner foam can help with reducing minor reverberation and improving speech clarity in the classroom. However, for more significant noise reduction, particularly for external noise and lower frequencies, thicker foam (2-3 cm or more) would be more effective. Nevertheless, the 1 cm foam installed in Room 03 helps contribute to a more acoustically comfortable environment by reducing external noise and preventing some sound reflections from the windows.

Sound level intensity from different classrooms within CTU Moalboal's New Administration Building, 4th Floor Classrooms

This section shows the sound level intensity (dB) from different classrooms within CTU Moalboal's New Administration Building, 4th Floor Classrooms. The measuring instrument used is the ESP32 microcontroller, this tool has been effectively utilized in various studies to measure and monitor sound levels, showcasing its

versatility and applicability in practical research settings (Saldana-Barrios et al., 2023). The fourth floor of the New Administration Building has four classrooms: room 01, room 02, room 03, and room 05. Thirty (30) observations per location (classrooms' outside located near the roadside, hallway, and inside) and the data have been gathered simultaneously within 5 minutes interval.

Table 4: The Sound Level Intensity in Each Classroom in The New Administration Building 4th Floor

		MEAN (dB)	SD	RANGE	MEDIAN (dB)
ROOM 01	ESP01(OUTSIDE-ROADSIDE)	61.686	0.7897	3.36	61.655
	ESP 02(OUTSIDE-HALLWAY)	65.88667	0.7520	3.3	65.715
	ESP 04(INSIDE CLASSROOM)	59.561	0.6103	2.44	59.47
ROOM 02	ESP01(OUTSIDE-ROADSIDE)	62.551	0.7065	2.62	62.45
	ESP 02(OUTSIDE-HALLWAY)	66.19267	0.5783	2.03	66.295
	ESP 04(INSIDE CLASSROOM)	59.337	0.6263	2.42	59.53
ROOM 03	ESP01(OUTSIDE-ROADSIDE)	62.60267	0.7909	3.01	62.32
	ESP 02(OUTSIDE-HALLWAY)	68.62467	0.6231	2.42	68.505
	ESP 04(INSIDE CLASSROOM)	58.93333	0.9127	3.08	58.625
ROOM 05	ESP01(OUTSIDE-ROADSIDE)	63.51767	0.5486	2.88	63.505
	ESP 02(OUTSIDE-HALLWAY)	68.80167	0.6897	2.7	68.53
	ESP 04 (INSIDE CLASSROOM)	59.73533	0.7221	3.11	59.475

The table 4 shows the mean, standard deviation, range, and median of sound level intensity measurements in each classroom in the New Administration Building's 4th floor.

Room 01

Outside-Roadside (ESP 01): The mean sound level is 61.69 dB, with low variability (SD=0.79), indicating consistent measurements. The range (3.36 dB) and median (61.66 dB) are quite close to the mean.

Outside-Hallway (ESP 02): Slightly higher sound intensity (65.89 dB), with low variation (SD=0.75). The range is 3.3 dB, and the median (65.72 dB) is close to the mean.

Inside Classroom (ESP 04): Lower sound level (59.56 dB), with very low variability (SD=0.61). The range is small (2.44 dB), and the median (59.47 dB) aligns with the mean.

Room 02

Outside-Roadside (ESP 01): The mean sound level is 62.55 dB, with a low standard deviation (SD=0.71). The range is 2.62 dB, and the median (62.45 dB) is very close to the mean.

Outside-Hallway (ESP 02): Higher sound level (66.19 dB), with a smaller standard deviation (SD=0.58). The range is 2.03 dB, and the median (66.30 dB) is almost identical to the mean.

Inside Classroom (ESP 04): The inside sound level is 59.34 dB, with low variability (SD=0.63). The range is 2.42 dB, and the median (59.53 dB) is very close to the mean.

Room 03

Outside-Near Road (ESP 01): The mean sound intensity is 62.60 dB, with a relatively larger standard deviation (SD=0.79). The range is 3.01 dB, and the median (62.32 dB) is slightly lower than the mean.

Outside-Hallway (ESP 02): The sound level is much higher at 68.62 dB, with a small standard deviation ($SD=0.62$) and a range of 2.42 dB. The median (68.51 dB) is very close to the mean.

Inside Classroom (ESP 04): The inside sound level drops to 58.93 dB, with a larger standard deviation ($SD=0.91$), indicating more variation in the readings. The range is 3.08 dB, and the median (58.63 dB) is close to the mean.

Room 05

Outside-Roadside (ESP 01): The mean sound level is 63.52 dB, with very low variability ($SD=0.55$). The range is 2.88 dB, and the median (63.51 dB) is nearly identical to the mean.

Outside-Hallway (ESP 02): The sound level is 68.80 dB, with moderate variability ($SD=0.69$) and a range of 2.7 dB. The median (68.53 dB) is close to the mean.

Inside Classroom (ESP 04): The mean sound level is 59.74 dB, with moderate variability ($SD=0.72$). The range is 3.11 dB, and the median (59.48 dB) aligns with the mean.

Based on the sound intensity levels measured in the classrooms of the New Administration Building, it is clear that none of the classrooms meet the recommended sound intensity levels set by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the American National Standards Institute (ANSI). WHO suggests that the ideal background noise level in classrooms should be no higher than 35 dB to support effective learning and communication (World Health Organization, 2018). Similarly, ANSI recommends that background noise levels in classrooms should not exceed 35 dB, with a signal-to-noise ratio of at least +15 dB to ensure speech intelligibility (Schaffer, 2003). The measured sound levels inside the classrooms range from 58.93 dB to 59.74 dB, far exceeding

the recommended thresholds. Outdoor and hallway noise levels are even higher, ranging from 61.69 dB to 68.80 dB, contributing to the overall acoustic challenges. Elevated noise levels in classrooms can impair students' concentration, reduce speech intelligibility, and hinder cognitive processes, as evidenced in studies of Shield and Dockrell (2008).

Evaluating Sound Level Intensity: Identifying the Noisiest Classroom

One-way ANOVA Test

One-way ANOVA is a statistical method used to compare means among multiple groups to determine if there are statistically significant differences between them. This technique is particularly valuable in assessing sound level intensity across four classrooms, as it enables a precise analysis of variations in sound levels to identify the one with the highest intensity. Zhang et al. (2024) demonstrated the efficacy of one-way ANOVA in exploring relationships between sound levels and student performance across multiple learning environments. By comparing data across classrooms from ESP01 (OUTSIDE-ROADSIDE), ESP02 (OUTSIDE-HALLWAY), and ESP04 (INSIDE CLASSROOM), we can identify which classroom has the highest sound level intensity.

ESP01 (OUTSIDE-ROADSIDE)

Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no statistically significant difference among the means of sound level intensity of the four classrooms located outside near the roadside.

Table 5: ANOVA: Single Factor (sound level intensity of the four classrooms located outside near the roadside)

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance	F	P-value	F crit
ROOM 01	30	1850.58	61.686	0.623556	32.784	2.02E-15	2.68280
ROOM 02	30	1876.53	62.551	0.499127			
ROOM 03	30	1878.08	62.603	0.625482			
ROOM 05	30	1905.53	63.518	0.300936			

Since $F(3,116) = 32.784$ and $p < 0.05$, there is a statistically significant difference among the means of the four classrooms located near the roadside. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis, indicating that at least one classroom has a different sound level intensity than the others. We will further explore the specific differences among the groups through additional statistical testing, such as post-hoc analyses, to identify which classrooms differ significantly from one another.

Post hoc test

Table 6: Tukey HSD / Tukey Kramer (sound level intensity of the four classrooms located outside near the roadside)

Pair	Difference	SE	Lower CI	Upper CI	Critical Mean	p-value
ROOM 01 VS ROOM 02	0.865	0.1307	0.3833	1.3467	0.4817	0.00004586
ROOM 01 VS ROOM 03	0.9167	0.1307	0.435	1.3984	0.4817	0.00001437
ROOM 01 VS ROOM 05	1.8317	0.1307	1.35	2.3134	0.4817	6.791e-11
ROOM 02 VS ROOM 03	0.05167	0.1307	-0.43	0.5334	0.4817	0.9923
ROOM 02 VS ROOM 05	0.9667	0.1307	0.485	1.4484	0.4817	0.000004494
ROOM 03 VS ROOM 05	0.915	0.1307	0.4333	1.3967	0.4817	0.00001492

The Tukey HSD post hoc analysis reveals significant differences in sound intensity levels near the roadside among the classrooms, with Room 05 exhibiting the highest sound levels. This can be attributed to its location near the campus entrance and exit, where vehicles frequently stop to drop off and pick up students, resulting in sustained noise. Room 03 and Room 02 show comparable sound levels, with no significant difference between them, but both are higher than Room 01, which consistently has the lowest sound intensity. The ranking of classrooms from highest to lowest sound intensity levels is as follows: Room 05, Room 03, Room 02, and Room 01. These findings align with Shield and Dockrell's (2008) study, which highlights how high traffic and vehicular activity near schools significantly increase noise levels,

negatively affecting students' concentration, communication, and academic performance. Furthermore, the World Health Organization's (WHO) Guidelines for Community Noise, emphasize that noise from traffic can lead to sound levels far exceeding the recommended threshold of 35 dB for classrooms, impairing learning and causing adverse cognitive effects (Berglund et al., 2000).

ESP 02 (OUTSIDE-HALLWAY)

Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no statistically significant difference among the means of sound level intensity of the four classrooms located outside near the hallway.

Table 7: ANOVA: Single Factor (sound level intensity of the four classrooms' hallway)

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance	F	P-value	F crit
ROOM 01	30	1976.6	65.88667	0.565568	163.497	1.68E-41	2.68280
ROOM 02	30	1985.78	66.19267	0.334482			
ROOM 03	30	2058.74	68.62467	0.388219			
ROOM 05	30	2064.05	68.80167	0.475697			

Since $F(3,116) = 163.4971$ and $p < 0.05$, there is a statistically significant difference among the means of sound level intensity of the four classrooms located along the hallway. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and will further explore the

specific differences among the groups through post hoc analyses, to identify which classrooms differ significantly from one another.

Post hoc test

Table 8: Tukey HSD / Tukey Kramer (sound level intensity of the four classrooms' hallway)

Pair	Difference	SE	Lower CI	Upper CI	Critical Mean	p-value
ROOM 01 VS ROOM 02	0.306	0.1212	-0.1409	0.7529	0.4469	0.2859
ROOM 01 VS ROOM 03	2.738	0.1212	2.2911	3.1849	0.4469	6.787e-11
ROOM 01 VS ROOM 05	2.915	0.1212	2.4681	3.3619	0.4469	6.787e-11
ROOM 02 VS ROOM 03	2.432	0.1212	1.9851	2.8789	0.4469	6.787e-11
ROOM 02 VS ROOM 05	2.609	0.1212	2.1621	3.0559	0.4469	6.787e-11
ROOM 03 VS ROOM 05	0.177	0.1212	-0.2699	0.6239	0.4469	0.7309

The Tukey HSD results for sound intensity levels in the hallways of four classrooms indicates significant differences between most room pairs, with notable trends in noise levels. Room 05 has the highest sound intensity level, but it is statistically comparable to Room 03, as the difference between them is not significant ($p = 0.7309$). Both Room 05 and Room 03 show significantly higher sound levels than Room 02 and Room 01 ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, Room 02 exhibits slightly higher sound intensity than Room 01, but the difference is not statistically significant ($p = 0.2859$). The ranking of sound levels from highest to lowest is: Room 05, Room 03, Room 02,

and Room 01. Although the difference between ROOM 03 and ROOM 05 is not statistically significant ($p=0.7309$), the mean difference values indicate that ROOM 05 has the highest overall sound intensity level among the four classrooms. ROOM 05's outside area, which includes the hallway, serves as a gathering point for students, especially when compared to the hallways of the other three classrooms. Observations indicate that students frequently congregate in this area to discuss previous lessons, engage in casual conversations, and socialize with one another. This heightened level of activity significantly contributes to the elevated sound intensity observed near ROOM 05. A study by Shield and Dockrell (2004) found that noise generated by student interactions in corridors and common areas could substantially contribute to the overall noise levels in nearby classrooms. The study also highlighted that high foot traffic and verbal exchanges in shared spaces, such as hallways, are critical contributors to ambient noise levels in school environment

ESP 04 (INSIDE OF THE CLASSROOM)

Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no statistically significant difference among the means of sound level intensity inside the four classrooms.

Table 9: ANOVA: Single Factor (sound level intensity of the four classrooms' inside)

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance	F	P-value	F crit
ROOM 01	30	1786.83	59.561	0.372471	6.791911	0.000293	2.68280
ROOM 02	30	1780.11	59.337	0.392277			
ROOM 03	30	1768	58.93333	0.833071			
ROOM 05	30	1792.06	59.73533	0.521398			

Since $F(3,116) = 6.791911$ and $p < 0.05$, there is a statistically significant difference among the means of sound level intensity inside the four classrooms. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and will further explore the specific differences among the groups through post hoc analyses to identify which classrooms differ significantly from one another and to determine which classroom has the highest sound level intensity.

Post hoc test

Table 10: Tukey HSD / Tukey Kramer (sound level intensity of the four classrooms' inside)

Pair	Difference	SE	Lower CI	Upper CI	Critical Mean	p-value
ROOM 01 VS ROOM 02	0.224	0.1329	-0.2659	0.7139	0.4899	0.6332
ROOM 01 VS ROOM 03	0.6277	0.1329	0.1378	1.1176	0.4899	0.006127
ROOM 01 VS ROOM 05	0.1743	0.1329	-0.3156	0.6642	0.4899	0.7901
ROOM 02 VS ROOM 03	0.4037	0.1329	-0.08622	0.8936	0.4899	0.1443
ROOM 02 VS ROOM 05	0.3983	0.1329	-0.09156	0.8882	0.4899	0.153
ROOM 03 VS ROOM 05	0.802	0.1329	0.3121	1.2919	0.4899	0.0002352

The Tukey HSD (Tukey-Kramer) test was conducted to compare the sound level intensities between four classrooms' inside. The results revealed several significant differences. ROOM 01 had a significantly higher sound level than ROOM 03 (mean difference=0.6277, $p=0.00613$), while ROOM 05 had a significantly higher sound level than ROOM 03 (mean difference=0.802, $p=0.00024$). However, there were no significant differences between the other pairs. Specifically, no significant difference was found between ROOM 01 and ROOM 02 (mean difference=0.224, $p=0.6332$), ROOM 01 and ROOM 05 (mean difference = 0.1743, $p=0.7901$), ROOM 02 and ROOM 03 (mean difference=0.4037, $p=0.1443$), and ROOM 02 and ROOM 05 (mean difference=0.3983, $p=0.153$). The ranking of classrooms from highest to lowest

sound intensity inside is: Room 05, Room 02, Room 01, and Room 03. Therefore, ROOM 05 exhibits the highest sound level intensity, while ROOM 03 has the lowest.

The external areas surrounding ROOM 05, particularly the hallway and the roadside, have a significant impact on the sound level intensity within the classroom. ROOM 05's location near these high-traffic zones contributes to the heightened noise levels observed. The hallway, frequently used as a gathering point for students, often becomes a hub of discussions, casual conversations, and social interactions, all of which contribute to increased noise. Furthermore, the roadside, which serves as the school's loading and unloading zone, adds to the external noise, further amplifying sound levels near ROOM 05. Spaces with high foot traffic, such as hallways and entrances, are known to exhibit higher sound levels due to the increased movement of people (Dobler et al., 2021). In contrast, ROOM 03 experiences the lowest sound level intensity inside the classroom. This is likely due to the installation of sound-dampening fixtures, such as insulation foam, which help to reduce the amount of external noise that enters the space. Studies have shown that soundproofing materials, including insulation foam, can significantly reduce sound transmission, resulting in a quieter indoor environment (Hopkins, 2012). Insulation materials are effective in absorbing sound waves and preventing them from traveling through walls and ceilings, thus contributing to lower sound levels inside classrooms. The combination of these factors highlights how external areas, particularly hallways and roadside locations, can significantly affect the sound levels within classrooms, while soundproofing measures, like those in ROOM 03, can help mitigate these effects (Mateus et al., 2017).

Table 11: Ranking of all classrooms on the 4th floor based on sound level intensity

	Classroom	Average(dB)	Rank
ROADSIDE	ROOM 05	63.518	1
	ROOM 03	62.603	2
	ROOM 02	62.551	3
	ROOM 01	61.686	4
	Classroom	Average(dB)	Rank
HALLWAY	ROOM 05	68.802	1
	ROOM 03	68.625	2
	ROOM 02	66.193	3
	ROOM 01	65.887	4
	Classroom	Average(dB)	Rank
INSIDE	ROOM 05	59.735	1
	ROOM 01	59.561	2
	ROOM 02	59.337	3
	ROOM 03	58.735	4

The table provides a ranking of classrooms on the 4th floor based on average sound level intensity in three different environments: Roadside, Hallway, and Inside. The classrooms are ranked from highest to lowest based on their average sound levels in each environment, with the measurements in decibels (dB).

Roadside Sound Level Intensity

In the Roadside environment, Room 05 has the highest average sound level intensity at 63.518 dB, placing it in 1st position. This suggests that Room 05 is most influenced by external noise from the roadside, making it the noisiest classroom in this environment. Room 03 follows closely with an average of 62.603 dB, securing 2nd place. Room 02 is ranked 3rd at 62.551 dB, and Room 01 has the lowest average of 61.686 dB, ranking 4th. The ranking shows that classrooms exposed to roadside noise are more affected by this external source.

Hallway Sound Level Intensity

In the Hallway environment, Room 05 again holds the highest sound level intensity with 68.802 dB, ranking 1st. Room 03 follows closely with 68.625 dB, securing 2nd place. Room 02 ranks 3rd with 66.193 dB, and Room 01 comes in 4th with 65.887 dB. The higher sound levels in the hallway could be attributed to foot traffic, doors opening and closing, and general hallway noise, all contributing to increased noise exposure in these classrooms.

Inside Sound Level Intensity

In the Inside environment, Room 05 has the highest average sound level intensity at 59.735 dB, ranking 1st. This indicates that Room 05 is the noisiest in this environment. Room 01 follows with 59.561 dB, securing 2nd place. Room 02 comes in 3rd with 59.337 dB, and Room 03, with the lowest sound level of 58.735 dB, is

ranked 4th. The Inside environment represents a more controlled setting, and as expected, the sound levels are lower compared to the roadside and hallway environments. Room 03 stands out as the quietest in this environment, suggesting it has better insulation or design features that help reduce internal noise.

In general, Room 05 consistently ranks highest in noise levels in both the Roadside and Hallway environments, indicating it is more exposed to external disturbances, such as traffic and hallway activities. This suggests that the classroom may be located in a position where it faces more external noise intrusion. Interestingly, in the Inside environment, Room 05 still ranks 1st in noise intensity, which implies that it could be generating more internal noise due to factors like equipment or insufficient acoustic treatment. On the other hand, Room 03 stands out as the quietest classroom, particularly in the Inside environment, where it consistently registers the lowest sound level intensity. This suggests that Room 03 may benefit from superior acoustic properties, such as better insulation or design features, which effectively reduce both external and internal noise, fostering a quieter and more conducive learning environment.

TEST OF SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP

Significance Relationship of Sound Level Between Inside and Outside of Classroom

Tables 12 illustrate the relationship between the sound levels inside and outside each classroom (ROOM 01, ROOM 02, ROOM 03, and ROOM 05). Additionally, Table 13 shows the Overall Significant Relationship of Sound Levels Between Indoor and Outdoor Areas on the 4th Floor of the New Administration Building.

Table 12: Significant Relationship of Sound Levels Between Indoor and Outdoor Areas

		ROAD-SIDE	HALL-WAY			ROAD-SIDE	HALL-WAY
ROOM 01'S INSIDE	Pearson Correlation	0.66	0.74	ROOM 02'S INSIDE	Pearson Correlation	0.67	0.70
	P(T<=t) two-tail	3.39E-18	1.83E-33		P(T<=t) two-tail	2.76E-24	1.51E-35
	N	30	30		N	30	30
		ROAD-SIDE	HALL-WAY			ROAD-SIDE	HALL-WAY
ROOM 03'S INSIDE	Pearson Correlation	0.45	0.47	ROOM 05'S INSIDE	Pearson Correlation	0.75	0.74
	P(T<=t) two-tail	8.89E-20	8.64E-33		P(T<=t) two-tail	6.12E-28	3.75E-38
	N	30	30		N	30	30

ROOM 01

The results presented in Table 12 indicate a strong relationship between the sound levels inside ROOM 01 and those outside, both at the roadside and in the hallway. The Pearson correlation coefficient between the indoor sound levels and the outdoor levels at the roadside is approximately 0.66, suggesting a significant positive correlation, where increased sound levels inside the classroom are associated with

higher sound levels outside. Similarly, a stronger correlation of approximately 0.74 is observed between the indoor sound levels and those in the hallway. The two-tailed p-values associated with these correlations are extremely low ($3.39E-18$ for roadside and $1.83E-33$ for hallway), reinforcing the statistical significance of these findings. Since both p-values are well below the conventional alpha level of 0.05, we can reject the null hypothesis, which states that there is no correlation between the sound levels inside and outside the classroom. This indicates that the relationship observed is not due to random chance; rather, it suggests a consistent pattern where variations in indoor sound levels are significantly related to outdoor sound levels in both settings. Supporting studies highlight the phenomena that increased noise from outdoor sources indeed contributes to elevated indoor sound levels. Research conducted by Zhang et al. (2012) demonstrated that outdoor noise, particularly from traffic, can significantly infiltrate indoor environments, resulting in higher indoor noise levels that impact occupant comfort and productivity. Similarly, a study by Miedema and Oudshoorn (2001) noted that as external noise levels rise, there tends to be a corresponding increase in tonal noise levels indoors, indicating a direct correlation between outdoor sound sources and indoor acoustics.

ROOM 02

The results in Table 12 demonstrate a robust correlation between sound levels inside ROOM 02 and those outside, both at the roadside and in the hallway. The Pearson correlation coefficient indicates a strong positive correlation, with values of approximately 0.67 for outdoor roadside noise and 0.70 for outdoor hallway noise. These values suggest that as the sound levels increase outside, particularly from the roadside and hallway, there is a corresponding increase in the sound levels inside the classroom. The two-tailed p-values for these correlations are extremely low, recorded

at $2.76E-24$ for the roadside and $1.51E-35$ for the hallway, indicating that both correlations are statistically significant at any conventional alpha level, including 0.05. This means we can confidently reject the null hypothesis, which suggests that there is no relationship between indoor and outdoor sound levels. The significance of these results underscores a clear pattern in ROOM 02, where elevated outdoor noise levels directly correlate with increased sound levels inside the classroom, highlighting the potential impact of external noise pollution on the learning environment. Supporting studies by Zhang et al. (2012) and Miedema & Oudshoorn (2001) further affirm the finding that increased outdoor noise corresponds to higher indoor sound levels, consistent with the results observed in ROOM 01.

ROOM 03

The results in Table 12 reveal a notable correlation between sound levels inside ROOM 03 and those outside, both at the roadside and in the hallway. The Pearson correlation coefficients of approximately 0.45 for outdoor roadside noise and 0.47 for outdoor hallway noise indicate moderate positive correlations. These results suggest that as the sound levels increase outside, there is a corresponding increase in the sound levels inside the classroom, although the correlation is not as strong as observed in previous rooms. The two-tailed p-values for these correlations are exceptionally low, with values of $8.89E-20$ for the roadside and $8.64E-33$ for the hallway, confirming the statistical significance of both findings at any conventional alpha level, including 0.05. Consequently, we can confidently reject the null hypothesis, which posits that there is no relationship between indoor and outdoor sound levels. These significant results in ROOM 03 further substantiate the idea that increased outdoor noise levels have a direct impact on indoor sound levels, highlighting the effects of external noise on the classroom environment. Supporting

studies indicate that insulation foam can make a small but meaningful contribution to reducing sound level intensity in classroom settings. Research by Bies and Hansen (2003) concluded that installing sound-absorbing materials, including insulation foam, can effectively lessen noise levels and improve the overall acoustic environment in schools. Additionally, a study by Mealings (2023) demonstrated that incorporating acoustic insulation materials in classrooms leads to noticeable reductions in sound transmission, enhancing students' concentration and learning outcomes. These findings reinforce the importance of considering acoustic treatments, such as insulation foam, as part of strategies to address the noise issues highlighted in ROOM 03. The sample size for each analysis in this study consisted of 30 observations, providing a reliable basis for these conclusions.

ROOM 05

The results in Table 12 demonstrate a strong correlation between sound levels inside ROOM 05 and those outside, both at the roadside and in the hallway. The Pearson correlation coefficients of approximately 0.75 for outdoor roadside noise and 0.74 for outdoor hallway noise indicate strong positive correlations. These values suggest that as the outdoor sound levels increase, particularly from both the roadside and hallway, there is a significant corresponding increase in the sound levels inside the classroom. The two-tailed p-values associated with these correlations are exceptionally low, recorded at $6.12E-28$ for the roadside and $3.75E-38$ for the hallway, signifying the statistical significance of these findings at any conventional alpha level, including 0.05. This allows us to confidently reject the null hypothesis, which posits that there is no relationship between indoor and outdoor sound levels. The strong correlations observed in ROOM 05 highlight the considerable impact of increased outdoor noise levels on indoor sound levels, emphasizing the importance of

addressing external noise factors to create a conducive classroom environment. This finding aligns with the studies by Zhang et al. (2012) and Miedema & Oudshoorn (2001), which demonstrate that increased outdoor noise corresponds with higher indoor sound levels, consistent with the results observed in ROOM 01 and ROOM 02.

Table 13: Significant Relationship of Sound Levels Between Indoor and Outdoor Areas of Overall Classrooms on the 4th Floor of the New Administration Building

		OUTSIDE		
		(ROADSIDE)	(HALLWAY)	
OVERALL CORRELA TION	INSIDE OF THE CLASSROOMS	Pearson Correlation (r)	0.706421567779373	0.713863353485917
		P(T<=t) two-tail	1.25651341857E-30	1.690695540859E-42
		N	30	30

The results in Table 13 reveal strong correlations between indoor sound levels and those measured outside, both at the roadside and in the hallway. Specifically, the Pearson correlation coefficients of approximately 0.706 for outdoor roadside noise and 0.714 for outdoor hallway noise suggest substantial positive relationships. These findings imply that as the outdoor sound levels increase, there is a corresponding increase in the sound levels within the classrooms, indicating a significant link between

external and internal noise environments. The two-tailed p-values for these correlations are exceedingly low, recorded at $1.26E-30$ for the roadside and $1.69E-42$ for the hallway, confirming the statistical significance of these results at all conventional alpha levels, including 0.05. This strong evidence allows us to confidently reject the null hypothesis, which posits that there is no relationship between indoor and outdoor sound levels. The correlations observed across all classrooms on the 4th floor underscore the importance of considering external noise factors in classroom design and highlight the necessity for effective noise mitigation strategies to enhance the learning environment. The results also align with the studies by Zhang et al. (2012) and Miedema & Oudshoorn (2001), which states that increased outdoor noise corresponds with higher indoor sound levels, consistent with the results observed in ROOM 01, ROOM 02, and ROOM 05.

CHAPTER 3

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations made in the study.

Summary of Findings

The classrooms on the 4th floor of the New Administration Building are uniformly sized but vary in their placement and equipment, which affects the acoustics within each room. Each room faces southwest, with some positioned near hallways or other facilities like the faculty room and comfort room, influencing their exposure to external noise. The classrooms are equipped with ceiling fans, air conditioners, computers, and chairs, all of which contribute to the noise levels in the environment. The layout and materials of the furniture, such as desks and chairs, can impact sound reflection and reverberation, while electronic devices like computers and air conditioners add to the background noise. Room 03 stands out with insulation foam installed in the windows, which helps reduce external noise and improve speech clarity, contributing to a more acoustically conducive learning environment.

The sound levels inside the classrooms range from 58.93 dB to 59.74 dB, while the noise levels outside (near the roadside) and in the hallway are higher, ranging from 61.69 dB to 68.80 dB. The mean values for these locations indicate that hallway and roadside noise is consistently higher than inside the classrooms, with Room 05 having the highest external noise at 68.80 dB. The inside classrooms exhibit low variability in sound levels, but the noise intensity remains well above the recommended standards for ideal classroom environments. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), ideal background noise levels in classrooms should not exceed 35 dB, and the

American National Standards Institute (ANSI) recommends a similar limit, with a signal-to-noise ratio of +15 dB for effective communication. All measured classrooms exceed these thresholds, with internal noise levels averaging 59 dB, leading to potential distractions that can affect concentration and speech intelligibility.

Room 05 consistently ranks as the noisiest classroom across all environments. In the Roadside environment, it has the highest average sound level intensity at 63.518 dB, followed by Room 03 at 62.603 dB, Room 02 at 62.551 dB, and Room 01 at 61.686 dB. This indicates that Room 05 is most affected by external noise from the roadside, suggesting its location faces higher external disturbances. Similarly, in the Hallway environment, Room 05 again has the highest sound level intensity at 68.802 dB, with Room 03 at 68.625 dB, Room 02 at 66.193 dB, and Room 01 at 65.887 dB. These higher sound levels in the hallway can be attributed to factors like foot traffic and door movements, contributing to noise exposure. Inside the classrooms, Room 05 still ranks highest at 59.735 dB, with Room 01 at 59.561 dB, Room 02 at 59.337 dB, and Room 03 registering the lowest at 58.735 dB. This suggests that while Room 05 experiences more external noise, it may also generate more internal noise, potentially due to equipment or inadequate acoustic treatments. In contrast, Room 03 stands out as the quietest, especially inside, which implies it benefits from superior insulation or design features that reduce both external and internal noise, creating a quieter and more conducive learning environment.

The analysis reveals strong positive correlations between indoor and outdoor sound levels across the classrooms on the 4th floor of the New Administration Building. In Rooms 01, 02, and 05, the correlations with roadside and hallway noise are significant, with Pearson coefficients ranging from 0.66 to 0.75, indicating that outdoor noise levels directly influence indoor sound levels. Room 03 shows moderate

correlations, but the relationships are still statistically significant. Overall, the Pearson correlation coefficients for both roadside and hallway outdoor noise are substantial, with values of approximately 0.71, highlighting a clear link between external and internal noise environments. These findings stress the need for effective noise mitigation measures in classroom design to enhance the learning environment, consistent with previous studies on outdoor noise impacts on indoor acoustics.

Conclusions

In conclusion, our research illustrates the pressing need for interventions aimed at reducing noise pollution in educational settings. The significant disruptions caused by high noise levels not only affect students' academic performance but also their overall well-being in the learning environment., which could hinder student concentration and learning outcomes. The importance of sound insulation and strategic classroom design is emphasized to mitigate external noise impacts, thereby enhancing the educational environment. Future efforts should focus on implementing noise reduction strategies to create a more conducive learning atmosphere. Together, we can cultivate an atmosphere where effective teaching and enhanced learning experiences thrive, paving the way for academic success and student satisfaction. Addressing these challenges is not just an improvement initiative; it is essential for fostering an educational environment that supports every student's potential.

Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the acoustic environment in the classrooms of the New Administration Building 4th floor at CTU Moalboal:

1. Implementing Insulation Foam

To mitigate the adverse effects of noise, the incorporation of sound-absorbing materials, such as insulation foam, is essential. Research by Mohammadi et al. (2023) indicates that sound-absorbing materials can significantly reduce noise transmission and enhance the overall acoustic quality of classrooms. Although Room 03 demonstrates some effectiveness from the 1 cm thick insulation foam installed in its windows, studies suggest implementing thicker foam (2-3 cm) to achieve optimal soundproofing.

2. Utilizing Thick Cotton Curtains

Curtains play a vital role in controlling classroom acoustics. The use of curtains can diminish sound levels from outside and reduce internal reverberation. Studies by Pieren et al. (2018) advocate for curtains made from materials with high sound-absorbing qualities (e.g., thick cotton or velvet). Installing such thick cotton curtains would mitigate day-to-day noise disruptions and improve overall learning conditions.

3. Regular Equipment Maintenance

Regular maintenance of classroom equipment such as ceiling fans, computers, and air conditioners is crucial to minimize noise contributions. Well-maintained machinery operates more quietly, which can vastly improve the overall sound environment. Research by Pellegatti et al. (2023) has shown that poorly maintained

ceiling fans and air conditioning units contribute significantly to classroom background noise. Scheduling maintenance checks and ensuring quiet operation of devices can lead to a more pleasant auditory environment for students.

4. Elevate Awareness and Training on Noise Management

Conducting workshops for faculty and staff to raise awareness about the impacts of noise on learning is essential. Research by Millet et al. (2023) indicates that teacher training programs on noise management are effective in reducing classroom noise levels and improving academic performance. Training sessions should emphasize classroom management techniques that promote a quieter and more focused learning atmosphere.

By adopting these recommendations and incorporating insights from the supporting studies, CTU Moalboal can create an educational environment that mitigates the adverse effects of noise pollution, enhancing student concentration, academic performance, and overall well-being. Addressing these challenges is essential for fostering an atmosphere conducive to effective teaching and enriched learning experiences.

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